

The Structure of Crotoflorine, an Isoquinolinedienone Alkaloid of *Croton sparsiflorus* Morung.

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Occurrence of crotoflorine, a new phenolic isoquinolinedienone alkaloid has been observed in *Croton sparsiflorus* Morung. As the base readily darkens in air, the properties and reactions of crotoflorine have been studied with its mono and diacetates for its structure elucidation. From a close inspection of the UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectral data of mono and diacetates of crotoflorine and from the studies of their various transformation reactions crotoflorine has been proved to be a proaporphine base which on acid catalysed transformation followed by basification yields a known aporphine alkaloid sparsiflorine. The sign and the position of the circular dichroism bands of crotoflorine diacetate confirm the configuration of the C-6a H in crotoflorine as α .

In continuation of our earlier publication¹, we like to place on record the isolation and structure elucidation of a new isoquinolinedienone alkaloid designated as crotoflorine from *Croton sparsiflorus* Morung. Due to instability of the free base, crotoflorine was isolated in the form of its stable mono- and di- acetates.

Crotoflorine monoacetate, $C_{19}H_{19}O_4N$ ($M^+ = 325$), m.p. 156° (dec.), $[\alpha]_D + 32.9^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) exhibits UV absorption, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 232 (sh) and 285μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.31 and 3.53) ;

$\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 250 (sh) and 304μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.17 and 3.66) strikingly similar to that of glaziovine². The IR spectrum of the acetate indicated the presence of a hydroxyl ($3.0-3.5 \mu$), a tertiary amide (6.18μ) and a conjugated carbonyl (6.02μ) function. The latter is associated with a cross-conjugated dienone system as evidenced from the N.M.R. spectrum of the acetate which shows two AB-type quartets at $6.30-6.63\delta$ and $6.85-7.15\delta$ integrating for four vinyl protons. The NMR spectrum of the acetate also reveals the presence of an aromatic methoxyl [3H(s) at 3.95δ], an $-N-C-CH_3$ grouping [3H (s)

at 22.2δ and a single aromatic proton at 6.82δ . The diacetate, $C_{21}H_{21}O_6N$ ($M^+ = 367$), m.p. 180° , $[\alpha]_D + 17.7^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), differs from the monoacetate by a phenolic acetate function as indicated from its UV [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 231 (sh) and 280μ ($\log \epsilon$,

4.38 and 3.58)] IR [λ_{max}^{KBr} 5.65 , $6.0-6.2$ and 8.35μ] and NMR [AB quartets at $6.20-6.38 \delta$ (H α and H α') and $6.66-7.04 \delta$ (H β and H β'); $J_{\alpha\beta} = J_{\alpha'\beta'} = 10$ cps ;

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$J_{\beta\beta'} = 3$ cps ; $J_{\alpha\alpha'} = 2$ cps ; 3H (s) at 3.77 δ (Ar-OCH₃), 2.18 δ ($\begin{array}{c} | \\ \text{N}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \\ || \\ \text{O} \end{array}$), and 2.06 δ (Ar-O-COCH₃) spectral data.

Catalytic hydrogenation of the monoacetate furnished a tetrahydro-derivative, C₁₉H₂₈O₄N (M⁺=329), m.p. 148°. The UV absorption, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 272 m μ (log ϵ , 3.45) ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH-NaOH}}$ 246 and 288 m μ (log ϵ , 3.97 and 3.76) of the compound is comparable to that of 2-methoxy-3, 4, 5-trimethyl-phenol². The IR spectrum of the tetrahydroderivative lacks the peak at 6.02 μ (conjugated >C=O) and instead, shows a new peak at 5.8 μ due to reduction of the cross-conjugated dienone system to a 6-ring ketone. This is consistent with the absence of the AB-quartets in the NMR spectrum of the compound. Similar catalytic hydrogenation of the diacetate afforded a tetrahydroderivative, C₂₁H₂₆O₅N (M⁺=371), m.p. 130° which also lacks the AB quartets in its NMR spectrum and shows infrared absorption at 5.85 μ .

Reduction of crotoflorine monoacetate with sodium boranate in methanol followed by treatment with mineral acid gave a compound, C₁₉H₁₉O₃N (M⁺=309), m.p. 265° (dec.). The UV spectrum, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 267 and 304 m μ (log ϵ , 4.20 and 3.76) is similar to that of 1, 2-oxygenated aporphines³. The compound shows no infrared absorption at 6.02 μ for the conjugated carbonyl. Such chemical transformation resulting in the formation of a product having 16 mass-unit less than the parent compound is reminiscent of dienol-benzene rearrangement³ of prosporphine alkaloids. Under identical reaction sequence crotoflorine-diacetate also furnished a deoxo-compound, C₂₁H₂₁O₄N (M⁺=351), m.p. 252°.

On the basis of the foregoing observations, structures I and II are assigned to the mono- and the di-acetate of crotoflorine respectively, - a conclusion which received

- I : R = H, R₁ = COCH₃
 II : R = R₁ = COCH₃
 VI : R = R₁ = H

- III : R = H, R₁ = R₂ = Me
 IV : R = Me, R₁ = R₂ = H
 V : R = R₁ = R₂ = Me

additional support from a detailed NMR spectral comparison of the two crotoflorine acetates with those of glaziovine³ (III), crotonasine⁴ (IV) and pronuciferine^{5,6} (V) and their appropriate derivatives. Therefore, VI appears to be the most logical

(VIII)

formulation for crotoflorine. The possibility of a salutaridine⁷-like structure (VII) for crotoflorine is ruled out by the fact that such a formulation would require an olefinic-aromatic proton ratio of 3:2 while crotoflorine acetates show a ratio of 4:1 in their NMR spectra. The relative positions of the methoxyl and hydroxyl groups in crotoflorine were finally settled by the acid-catalysed transformation of the alkaloid to a base (VIII), the hydrochloride of which was found to be identical in all respects with sparsiflorine hydrochloride¹, m.p. 278° (dec.).

The α -configuration* of the C-6aH in crotoflorine followed from a comparison of the sign and the position of the circular dichroism bands of crotoflorine diacetate [$\lambda(\Delta\epsilon)$: 300 (-0.39), 310 (-0.20), 320 (0), 330 (+0.12), 240 (+0.17), 350 (+0.14), 360 (+0.08), 370 (+0.04), 380 (+0.02), 400 (+0.01); (C, 4.13g/litre in methanol; cell length 1 cm; temperature 28.5°)] with those of a number of proaporphine alkaloids⁸.

The structure, VI for crotoflorine, thus established, is consistent with the mass fragmentations of crotoflorine diacetate, the fragmentation pattern being similar to that of crotonosine N, O-diacetate⁹. Besides the molecular ion peak ($M^+ = 367$), the

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* The C-6aH of sparsiflorine has since been established as α the details of which would be published elsewhere.

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mass spectrum of crotoflorine diacetate exhibits several important peaks at m/e 325 (M-42), 324 (M-43), 308, 296, 295, 282, 266, 254, 253, 239, 195, 165 and 43.

Crotoflorine is, therefore, a new addition to the growing list of biogenetically^{10,11} important proaporphine alkaloids which are very few in number.

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